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**12.00.08-УГОЛОВНОЕ ПРАВО. КРИМИНОЛОГИЯ.
УГОЛОВНО-ИСПОЛНИТЕЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО**

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GIFT-BASED MONEY LAUNDERING

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ANNOTATION

The article delves into the global phenomenon of money laundering, recognized by the international community, including the United Nations, as a prevalent and perilous transnational crime. The escalating threat of legitimizing criminal gains worldwide is a concern shared by the majority of countries. According to experts, recent years have seen criminal proceeds from various illicit activities in money laundering accounting for 2 to 5% of the global gross product, equating to 1 to 3 trillion US dollars. With the globalization of financial systems, there arises a need for coordinated international efforts to combat money laundering. Emphasis is placed on crime prevention, just sentencing, and the alignment of criminal legislation with international standards. Consequently, research is vital for defining accountability for laundering criminal proceeds, addressing contributing factors, ensuring proper legal classification, and bolstering adherence to international norms in national laws.

Until today, the phenomenon of money laundering through the provision of gifts has been little studied. Receiving and giving gifts may be one of the hidden methods and means of laundering criminal proceeds.

Keywords: crime, criminal liability, proceeds of crime, money laundering, legalization, punishment

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada xalqaro hamjamiyat, jumladan, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti tomonidan keng tarqalgan va xavfli transmilliy jinoyat sifatida tan olingan pul yuvishning global hodisasi batafsil yoritilgan. Dunyo bo‘ylab jinoiy daromadlarni qonuniylashtirish tahdidining kuchayishi ko‘pchilik mamlakatlarni tashvishga solmoqda. Mutaxassislarining fikricha, so‘nggi yillarda jinoiy daromadlar jinoiy daromadlarni legallashtirish bo‘yicha turli noqonuniy faoliyatdan olingan bo‘lib, bu jahon yalpi mahsulotining 2-5 foizini, ya‘ni 1-3 trillion AQSH dollariga teng. Moliyaviy tizimlarning globallashuvi bilan jinoiy daromadlarni legallashtirishga qarshi kurash bo‘yicha muvofiqlashtirilgan xalqaro sa‘y-harakatlarga ehtiyoj paydo bo‘ladi. Huquqbuzarliklarning oldini olish, adolatli jazo tayinlash, jinoyat qonunchiligini xalqaro standartlarga moslashtirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda. Binobarin, tadqiqot jinoiy daromadlarni legallashtirish uchun javobgarlikni aniqlash, yordam beruvchi omillarni bartaraf etish, to‘g‘ri huquqiy tasnifni ta‘minlash va milliy qonunlarda xalqaro normalarga rioya qilishni kuchaytirish uchun juda muhimdir.

Bugungi kunga qadar sovg'alarni taqdim etish orqali pul yuvish hodisasi kam o‘rganilgan. Sovg'alarni olish va berish jinoiy daromadlarni legallashtirishning yashirin usullari va vositalaridan biri bo‘lishi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: jinoyat, jinoiy javobgarlik, jinoiy daromadlar, pul yuvish, legallashtirish, jazo.

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ОТМЫВАНИЕ ДЕНЕГ, ОСНОВАННОЕ НА ПОДАРКАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается глобальное явление отмывания денег, признанное международным сообществом, в том числе Организацией Объединенных Наций, распространенным и опасным транснациональным преступлением. Растущая угроза легализации преступных доходов во всем мире является проблемой, разделяемой большинством стран. По оценкам экспертов, в последние годы преступные доходы от различных видов незаконной деятельности по отмыванию денег составляют от 2 до 5% мирового валового продукта, что соответствует 1-3 триллионам долларов США. С глобализацией финансовых систем возникает необходимость в скоординированных международных усилиях по борьбе с отмыванием денег. Особое внимание уделяется предупреждению преступности, справедливому наказанию и приведению уголовного законодательства в соответствие с международными стандартами. Следовательно, исследования имеют жизненно важное значение для определения ответственности за отмывание преступных доходов, устранения способствующих факторов, обеспечения надлежащей правовой классификации и обеспечения соблюдения международных норм в национальных законах.

До сегодняшнего дня малоизучено такое явление как отмывание денег путем предоставления подарков. Получение и предоставление подарков могут быть одним из скрытых методов и способов легализации преступных доходов.

Ключевые слова: преступление, уголовная ответственность, преступные доходы, отмывание денег, легализация, наказание.

Introduction

In recent years, the issue of money laundering has escalated into a significant concern for organizations and governments worldwide. Its prevalence has surged, transcending national boundaries to become a pervasive global challenge impacting individuals, states, and nations alike. This criminal phenomenon now presents challenges that exceed the capacity of any single jurisdiction, necessitating robust international collaboration for effective counteraction.

Consequently, concerted efforts have been redirected towards the formulation of comprehensive strategies and mechanisms aimed at thwarting and uncovering instances of money laundering. Moreover, there's a heightened focus on delving into the intricate legal ramifications and repercussions associated with this illicit activity.

Money laundering, frequently conducted through electronic means like anonymously depositing illicit funds in banks, represents just one facet of a broader spectrum of criminal behavior. It entails leveraging illegally acquired funds and directing them through various financial maneuvers, including entrepreneurship, transfers, and management. By converting dirty money into seemingly legitimate business assets, perpetrators obscure the funds' illicit origins and evade detection. The electronic nature of this process, often facilitated through banking systems, enables criminals to obscure their identities and evade scrutiny more easily.

There's an escalating imperative to bolster laws and regulations to forestall and uncover instances of money laundering, ensuring that those involved are held accountable for their actions.

The roots of money laundering trace back to the 1920s in the United States, notably associated with criminal syndicates like the American mafia. These organizations amassed profits from illicit endeavors such as robbery, prostitution, gambling, and drug trafficking. To legitimize their gains, they adopted a strategy of integrating the illegal proceeds with profits from bona fide enterprises they acquired. This fusion enabled them to launder their ill-gotten gains and obfuscate the true origins of their income.

Among the various fronts utilized for money laundering, the laundry industry, particularly laundromats, emerged as a favored avenue during that era. Criminal outfits heavily invested in this sector, leveraging it to veil their unlawful operations and present a facade of legitimacy. Money laundering, fundamentally involving the camouflage or transformation of criminal proceeds into lawful assets or income, persists as a formidable menace to the global economy. Efforts to combat this threat remain dynamic, evolving through ongoing enhancements in legal frameworks and regulatory protocols.

Materials and methods

The article employed several general scientific methods, including historical, comparative legal, and logical methods such as analysis and synthesis.

Research results

The Vienna Convention delineates a pathway for the implementation of a framework aimed at preventing money laundering, primarily through the involvement of law enforcement and regulatory bodies. The regulatory essence of anti-money laundering laws is geared towards incapacitating criminals, necessitating the identification, apprehension, and incarceration of offenders. The regulatory framework of anti-money laundering operates on the premise of either voluntary adherence to regulations or facing punitive measures for non-compliance [1].

Two significant contributions to countering the legalization of criminal proceeds were made through two UN Conventions: the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, adopted on November 15, 2000, and the UN Convention against Corruption, adopted on October 31, 2003 [2,3].

Additionally, the Financial Action Task Force on Money Laundering (FATF), acknowledged as the global standard setter for anti-money laundering endeavors, offers a concise definition of money laundering. According to FATF, money laundering entails the processing of criminal proceeds to conceal their illicit origins, thereby legitimizing the gains derived from criminal activities [4].

In legal science, there exist concepts suggesting that the act of "laundering" revenue inherently involves a fundamental objective – namely, to fabricate the facade of legality around income that is evidently derived from criminal activities [5, p.100].

In modern history, the term "money laundering" was first used in the late twentieth century in the United States of America in relation to the proceeds of drug trafficking [6]

Taking into account these facts, all this leads to the transformation of legalization into a highly profitable and effective criminal production [7, p.6]

Money laundering was historically associated primarily with serious crimes like drug trafficking. However, today it's widely understood as an integral component of more extensive criminal operations. In certain nations, money laundering is intertwined with corruption due to the intricate financial maneuvers involved in transferring illicit funds. These transactions deliberately obscure the funds' origins, complicating efforts to trace them back to their illegal source. Experts in money laundering exploit this complexity to effectively "clean" illicit funds. Consequently, there's an increasing imperative for stricter measures and international collaboration to counter the proliferation of money laundering activities and ensure accountability for those involved.

In Uzbekistan, the monetary system operates under a free foreign exchange regime, facilitating unrestricted transactions within the domestic banking system. Given the typical association of money laundering with criminal activities, combating this practice is pivotal in addressing organized crime, including corruption, bribery, smuggling, human trafficking, arms trading, terrorism, theft, embezzlement, fraud, forgery, gambling, prostitution, taxation, forestry, and environmental crimes. It's crucial to recognize that the nature and scale of money laundering in Uzbekistan may differ from other regions, with associated criminal activities evolving over time. Therefore, ongoing review and adaptation of anti-money laundering measures are essential to effectively combat this criminal activity.

In contemporary society, there's a growing push for innovative thinking. The notion of rewards has evolved beyond its traditional connotations. Previously, rewards for positive interactions were granted without bias or group interests. However, today, various symbols of human prestige are associated with socially justifiable reasons.

Moreover, the modern interpretation of a "gift" often implies a present given with the intention of influencing a decision, typically wielded by the recipient's position-specific authority. Yet, not all individuals perceive gifts as bearing ulterior motives. One unresolved issue in Uzbekistan is the challenge of money laundering, frequently referenced in the media through terms like "money laundering," "cleaning money," "laundering money," or "illegal (dirty) transactions." Broadly, "money laundering" denotes the act of converting assets derived from non-criminal activities into legitimate funds through various means, allowing for the concealment of the assets' true origins.

The Ministry of Justice of Uzbekistan has recently recorded an order from the Director of the Anti-Corruption Agency, outlining protocols for the giving and receiving of gifts by government officials during official trips and international engagements.

As per the directive, government officials are barred from accepting gifts in exchange for carrying out or abstaining from their duties in favor of individuals or legal entities. However, gifts granted for outstanding service based on a government agency's decision, as well as those bestowed for achievements in competitions, state holidays, official commemorations, and similar events, fall outside this prohibition.

Government officials are permitted to receive gifts while on official trips abroad, participating in international gatherings, or attending other official functions, including those within Uzbekistan. Nevertheless, these gifts must adhere to Uzbekistan's legislative requirements and the internal departmental regulations of the government entity. They should be voluntarily given in connection to a specific international or official occasion. Furthermore, gifts must not engender conflicts of interest or corruption risks; specifically, they must not impose obligations that could compromise impartial decision-making.

It's crucial for government officials to receive gifts with transparency and integrity, ensuring that the reputation of their agency remains untarnished. It's strictly prohibited for officials to solicit or expect gifts while representing their country on official trips or at international gatherings.

To maintain accountability, officials have the right to ask for documentation from the donor validating the value of any received gifts, be it in the form of cash receipts, goods receipts, or any other pertinent records.

It's worth noting that certain items, such as flowers, food items like pastries, and office supplies such as calendars, brochures, pens, and notebooks provided by organizations, are exempt from being classified as gifts. Therefore, they do not need to be formally registered as such.

Upon returning from a business trip, employees are required to promptly submit a report detailing any gifts received within three working days. This report should be directed to the internal control entity within the government agency tasked with combating corruption.

In instances where a receipt or invoice is unavailable, the value of the gift is determined either internally or through external expertise. This assessment may encompass market value evaluations conducted via various channels, including trade points, online resources, and other reliable sources.

If the assessed value of the gift falls below four times the basic calculation value (1.2 million soums), it remains the property of the employee, notwithstanding that the project initially stipulated a sum five times the basic calculation value. However, if the value exceeds four times the basic calculation value, the gift is then transferred to the government agency's inventory and may be utilized to meet the agency's operational needs.

The enactment of the Law on State Civil Service, effective as of November 10, 2022, underscores the commitment to combating corruption within the realm of state civil service. One of the pivotal measures outlined within this law is the establishment of protocols governing the receipt and delivery of gifts to civil servants. This initiative is part of a broader framework aimed at thwarting corrupt practices among civil servants.

Among the multifaceted strategies outlined in the law are initiatives to proactively prevent corrupt behavior among civil servants. This encompasses measures to uphold ethical standards of conduct, create robust organizational and legal structures for identifying and mitigating conflicts of interest within the civil service sector, implement systems for the declaration of income and assets, and provide comprehensive social protection, material support, and incentives for civil servants.

By implementing these measures, the law seeks to foster transparency, integrity, and accountability within the state civil service, thereby fortifying efforts to combat corruption and uphold the principles of good governance. [8, p.19]. These measures also relate to combating money laundering.

In Uzbekistan, ongoing efforts are being made to address white-collar crimes, which encompass fraudulent decisions made by influential individuals in both government and private sectors, impacting financial matters. Money laundering typically ensues such financial crimes, underscoring the interconnectedness between mandatory anti-money laundering laws and various white-collar crime issues, including corruption, banking offenses, and illicit activities.

Recent years have witnessed intensified endeavors to enforce regulations aimed at preventing money laundering. The imperative lies in curtailing criminals' ability to reap the rewards of their illicit activities. To this end, a transaction reporting system has been established to flag instances of money laundering.

It's worth noting that the nature and scale of money laundering in Uzbekistan may diverge from trends observed in other regions. Moreover, the dynamic landscape of crime necessitates a continuous reassessment and refinement of anti-money laundering measures to effectively combat this illicit practice.

Asset and property confiscation constitutes a common practice in Uzbekistan for individuals convicted of crimes. Nonetheless, challenges persist regarding money laundering, particularly concerning the legal framework employed by law enforcement agencies to detect and prosecute offenders. Additionally, hurdles related to employment, law enforcement practices, and cultural norms within the community exacerbate these issues.

The existing legal framework in Uzbekistan is marred by limitations, ambiguities, and contradictions, affecting both substantive and procedural regulations. Regrettably, the enforcement of money laundering laws often fails to strike a fair balance between the rights of the accused and the broader interests of society. Instances have arisen where individuals unwittingly received gifts or rewards acquired through money laundering and found themselves wrongly implicated in the crime. Central to these cases is the question of whether the individual was aware of the illicit origin of the proceeds. In cases where there was no awareness, individuals may still face repercussions for their involvement.

According to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, money laundering involves the process of giving a seemingly lawful appearance to property, including money or other assets, acquired from criminal activities. This is achieved through their transfer, conversion, or exchange, as well as by concealing or obscuring the true nature, source, location, method of disposal, movement, or legitimate rights associated with the money or assets, if derived from criminal activities.

In contemporary times, the utilization of electronic media is prevalent among individuals. However, it's regrettably not uncommon for electronic and mass media to be misused, with money laundering being a notable example. Money laundering crimes may be driven by intentional motives or arise as a natural consequence of illicit activities.

In accordance with Uzbekistan's legal framework, direct utilization of proceeds obtained through illicit means is prohibited. Money laundering can be delineated into three distinct forms, the first being active money laundering:

Active money laundering involves actions taken by individuals to place, transfer, issue, convert, or exchange money or securities derived from illicit activities, with the explicit intent of concealing the origins of these assets. [9].

Passive money laundering entails individuals who receive or exercise control over proceeds acquired from money laundering activities [10].

In alignment with the laws of Uzbekistan, money laundering unfolds through three distinct stages:

The first stage, known as "placement," involves the initial transfer of illicit funds acquired from criminal activities. This can be achieved through various means, including physically transporting cash in small increments, depositing it into the banking system, or clandestinely smuggling it across borders.

Layering involves the intricate process of obfuscating the origin of illicit funds by establishing a convoluted network of financial transactions. This intricate web serves to eradicate any traces of the money trail, ensuring anonymity for the individuals involved.

Integration, on the other hand, entails taking the proceeds of criminal activity and funneling them through the placement and layering stages. This transforms the illicit funds into investments that appear legitimate. Throughout this phase, the funds or assets seamlessly merge into the existing financial system, indistinguishable from other lawful assets.

Monetary settlement serves as a mechanism to conceal or disguise the profits obtained from a predicate offense, thereby preventing their detection and subsequent use as incriminating evidence. This technique is commonly employed across a spectrum of financial crimes, including white-collar offenses, to mask the illicit gains and evade legal consequences. Essentially, monetary settlement serves as a means to evade accountability for financial wrongdoing.

According to Article 243 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the maximum penalty for money laundering is 10 years of imprisonment.

The investigation focuses not only on the financial impact but also on the non-financial impact. As protecting the public's interests is a fundamental national ethical principle, the criminalization of money laundering is a necessary concept that should apply to business actors.

The application and criminal liability of money laundering vary across different laws, leading to discrepancies in their enforcement. These disparities can arise from various factors, such as laws that mention money laundering only as a subject matter without elaborating on the associated criminal penalties. Similarly, some laws regulate the criminal penalties but do not specify the representation

of money laundering in criminal proceedings. Consequently, it becomes challenging to establish a standardized approach to prosecuting money laundering offenses. To ensure consistency in the application of criminal liability for money laundering, there is a need for harmonization of laws that regulate money laundering and the associated penalties. This can involve streamlining the criminal proceedings and penalties for all offenses related to money laundering. Such measures can help to strengthen the effectiveness of anti-money laundering efforts, thus preventing financial crimes and protecting the integrity of the financial system.

The existence of differences in the application and criminal liability of money laundering according to various laws that regulate this criminal act can result in uncertainty and inconsistencies in the legal system. Such disparities can be observed in various aspects, including laws that only mention money laundering as a subject without further elaboration on criminal penalties, or laws that regulate criminal penalties without addressing the representation of money laundering in criminal proceedings. This uncertainty can be particularly concerning when it comes to determining the position of money laundering as a criminal act and the legal consequences that apply to money launderers and their accomplices.

Furthermore, the lack of consistency in defining, applying, and assigning criminal liability for money laundering exacerbates the challenges in identifying, prosecuting, and penalizing those involved in such illicit activities. It is imperative to establish coherent and uniform legal frameworks and guidelines that comprehensively address all aspects of money laundering, encompassing its definition, legal repercussions, and the roles and obligations of various stakeholders engaged in combating this unlawful practice.

Moreover, given the intricate nature of money laundering and its capacity to fuel a myriad of other criminal enterprises, adopting a holistic and coordinated strategy is paramount. Such an approach necessitates a multifaceted approach, including bolstered international cooperation, fortified regulatory frameworks, and heightened awareness and education initiatives targeting pertinent stakeholders, including financial institutions, law enforcement bodies, and the general populace.

Ultimately, the disparities in the application and criminal ramifications of money laundering across diverse legal systems and jurisdictions can significantly undermine efforts to combat this illicit activity effectively. Hence, concerted efforts must be directed towards establishing transparent and consistent legal frameworks that furnish a robust and harmonized response to money laundering and its associated criminal undertakings.

In Uzbekistan, regulations mandate the reporting of financial transactions involving assets suspected of originating from criminal activities. Suspicious financial transactions can be identified based on various general indicators, including a lack of discernible economic or business purpose, the use of substantial amounts of cash, abnormal criteria, and customer trading activities that deviate from established norms and appear unreasonable.

Financial transactions play a pivotal role in all business endeavors, necessitating thorough checks to prevent money laundering. Perpetrators of money laundering typically refrain from immediately utilizing the proceeds of their crimes; instead, they endeavor to obfuscate the funds' origins to impart a guise of legitimacy. Moreover, they may judiciously employ their illicit funds to sustain their operations clandestinely. Hence, it is paramount to report any suspicious financial transactions to forestall or combat criminal spending and fundraising. Nonetheless, it's important to recognize that not all financial transactions constitute criminal activities. Legitimate transactions, such as asset sales, are regarded as private undertakings and need not be reported. However, financial service providers are obligated by law in Uzbekistan to report transactions that arouse suspicion, such as those lacking clear economic or business rationale, involving significant cash sums, or diverging from established norms.

Issues may arise in financial transactions, such as instances where the recipient receives a gift from a family member that exceeds its value or when there exists an agency relationship between the provider and the recipient. Before labeling such transactions as money laundering, it's imperative to ascertain whether they contravene established rules. If deemed inappropriate, the recipient should

either decline the transaction or report it to the relevant authorities. Additionally, if the grant carries significant implications for the donor, the recipient should have the option to refuse or report it. Conversely, if the recipient repeatedly receives gifts from the same provider, they should assess the necessity of reporting such transactions.

Criminal proceeds denote assets derived from illegal activities, including corruption, which is punishable under Uzbekistan's legal statutes. It is imperative to prevent criminals from reaping the benefits of their illicit activities and to promptly report any suspicious financial transactions to the authorities to combat money laundering effectively.

The repercussions of money laundering can be profoundly detrimental to the nation and its communities, particularly when perpetrated by individuals within the community. Such offenses can exact a toll on the economy and must be preempted in accordance with the laws of Uzbekistan.

Embezzlement can be defined as the intentional control or appropriation of an object or asset derived from a criminal act, whether wholly or partially. However, it's important to note that receiving a gift from someone does not automatically imply that the gift is a result of embezzlement. Embezzlement entails a breach of trust, whereby an individual in possession of the goods abuses the trust placed in them by others.

There are no specific criteria to pinpoint funds derived from money laundering activities. However, authorities may flag individuals who receive proceeds from such crimes based on indicators like unusual financial growth or alterations in their financial records. Nevertheless, these indicators do not definitively indicate that an individual has received funds from money laundering activities. Law enforcement agencies must undertake thorough investigations in accordance with Uzbekistan's laws to apprehend individuals involved in money laundering crimes.

Conclusions

Money laundering through gift-giving presents various avenues for individuals to conceal illicit funds and make them appear legitimate. Here are some methods by which this can occur:

1. Gifts in exchange for services: Money laundering can occur when gifts are given in exchange for services rendered. For instance, a company may receive funds from a counterparty and subsequently transfer a portion of these funds as payment for services rendered. To conceal the illegal origin of the funds, the company may then present the counterparty with a gift exceeding the value of the services provided.

2. Gifts to family and friends: Another method involves giving gifts to close relatives or friends. For example, an individual may provide money to family members or friends as a gift for a birthday or holiday celebration. Despite potentially being obtained from dishonest or illegal sources, these funds appear as clean money that can be utilized without suspicion.

3. Charitable gifts: Money laundering may also occur through charitable donations. For instance, an individual may donate a significant sum to a charitable organization, enabling the organization to utilize the funds for its intended purposes. Subsequently, the individual may receive a portion or all of the donated funds back in the form of gifts from the charitable organization, thus obscuring the illicit origin of the money.

4. Gifts in exchange for purchases: Laundering money can involve purchasing goods from a company and receiving a gift exceeding the purchase price. For example, an individual may buy a car and receive a gift in return, such as a lavish vacation at an upscale resort, surpassing the cost of the car.

5. Gifts in exchange for investments: Another method involves giving money as an investment and then receiving the funds back in the form of gifts. For instance, an individual may invest money in a company and subsequently receive a gift exceeding the initial investment amount.

To enhance the effectiveness of Uzbekistan's Criminal Code in combating money laundering through gift-giving, it is recommended to consider specific provisions addressing these methods. Clear definitions, stringent penalties, and comprehensive investigative procedures can strengthen the legal framework and deter individuals from engaging in such illicit activities. Additionally, regular

reviews and updates to the Criminal Code to adapt to evolving methods of money laundering are essential in ensuring its relevance and efficacy in combating financial crimes.

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